

Effectiveness of Papworth Method on selected respiratory parameters among patients with COPD admitted in hospitals of selected areas

Mr. Sachin Waghmare¹, Mrs. Swati Gorad²

1. M.Sc. Nursing, Medical Surgical Nursing (CVTN), Sinhgad College of Nursing
2. Assistant Professor, Sinhgad College of Nursing

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ABSTRACT

According to World Health Organization COPD is fourth leading cause of death worldwide. Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is chronic, progressive lung disease that cause difficulty in breathing and is associated with significant decrease in lung function. The Papworth Method is a breathing technique that focuses on diaphragmatic breathing, nasal breathing and controlled exhalation. The objective of study was to assess effectiveness of Papworth Method on selected respiratory parameters among patients with COPD. A Quantitative research approach adopted. Pre-experimental one group pre-test post-test research design was used. 35 were selected by using a non-probability convenient sampling technique. Data were collected using Modified Borg Dyspnea Scale and pulse oximeter and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics including fisher's exact test. The accessible population consisted of patients with COPD admitted in hospitals of selected areas. As an intervention Papworth Method implemented, it was evident that the Papworth Method was significantly effective in improving selected respiratory parameters among patients with COPD. The study result revealed that the before implementation of the Papworth Method, the majority of patients with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease exhibited moderate (57.1%) to severe dyspnea (34.3%), with 97.1% having abnormal respiratory rate and 100% demonstrating abnormal SpO₂ levels. Following the intervention, marked clinical improvement was observed. Dyspnea levels shifted, with 8.6% reporting no dyspnea, 62.9% mild dyspnea and only 28.6% moderate dyspnea. The proportion of patients with normal respiratory rate increased substantially to 82.9%, while 42.9% achieved normal SpO₂ levels. Paired *t*-test analysis revealed statistically significant improvements across all parameters. Mean dyspnea score decreased from 5.7 to 2.5 ($t = 30.9, p < 0.05$), mean respiratory rate reduced from 25 to 18.6 ($t = 27.1, p < 0.05$) and mean SpO₂ increased from 90.1 to 93.9 ($t = 20.2, p < 0.05$). These findings indicate that the Papworth Method is highly effective in improving respiratory parameters among patients with COPD.

KEYWORDS: *Papworth Method, selected respiratory parameters, COPD.*

INTRODUCTION:

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is chronic, progressive lung disease that cause difficulty in breathing and is associated with significant decrease in lung function. COPD may include diseases that cause airflow obstruction (eg. emphysema, chronic bronchitis). Other diseases such as cystic fibrosis, bronchiectasis and asthma were previously classified as types of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Asthma is now considered as separate lung disorder and is classified as an abnormal airway condition characterized primarily by reversible inflammation. COPD can coexist with asthma. Both of these diseases have same majority of symptoms. Common symptoms of COPD develop from mid-life onwards. Patients with COPD experiences symptoms like difficulty in breathing, wheezing and chronic cough, which impact their quality of life and increase the risk of mortality.

According to World Health Organization COPD is fourth leading cause of death worldwide, causing 3.5 million deaths in 2021, approximately 5% of all global deaths. COPD is the eighth leading cause of poor health worldwide and nearly 90% of COPD deaths in those under 70 years of age occur in low-and-middle income countries. Tobacco smoking accounts for more than 70% of COPD cases in high income countries. In low- and middle-income countries tobacco smoking accounts for 30-40% of COPD cases and household air pollution (chulha) is major risk factor. Management of COPD typically involves medications, pulmonary rehabilitation and lifestyle changes. However, newer breathing techniques, such as the Papworth Method, have been proposed as effective complementary therapies for improving respiratory function and quality of life.

In India about 55.3 million cases of COPD were recorded in 2016 with a prevalence rate of 4.2% among those 30 years of age and above. According to studies on urban areas, Delhi has a 10% prevalence. Research conducted in rural regions revealed a 5.1% prevalence with females at 3.4% and males at 6.5%. Interestingly, people who had never smoked accounted for 85% of all cases. With 98 deaths from COPD per 100,000 people in 2019, India's rate was three times higher than that of the United States and the United Kingdom. With around 0.85 million fatalities from COPD in 2017, India was responsible for almost 30.28% of all COPD-related deaths worldwide.

In recent years, breathing retraining techniques have gained attention as complementary interventions to help COPD patients manage their symptoms more effectively. Among these, the Papworth Method a form of breathing therapy that emphasizes diaphragmatic breathing, nasal breathing and relaxation techniques has been identified as a potentially effective approach to improve breathing efficiency, exercise capacity and dyspnea. The Papworth Method is based on the premise that improving breathing patterns can help patients reduce hyperventilation, optimize oxygen exchange and manage anxiety associated with breathlessness.

Research on effectiveness of the Papworth Method in COPD patients has shown promising results, particularly in improving spirometry values (such as FEV1 and FVC), dyspnea and exercise tolerance.

Papworth Method is a breathing technique that focuses on diaphragmatic breathing, nasal breathing and controlled exhalation.

METHODS:

Study Design: Pre-experimental one group pre-test post-test research design.

Research Approach: The research methodology adopted for the study employed a quantitative research approach.

Setting: Hospitals of selected areas.

Sampling technique: Non-probability, convenient sampling technique.

Population: Patients with COPD.

Study Protocol: Before the data collection, consent was taken from the participants. The pre-test was conducted before the implementation of the intervention (Papworth Method). Post-intervention on selected respiratory parameters among patients with COPD were assessed. The data was collected from 05/12/2025 to 02/01/2026.

Data collection:

Section A – Semi-structured Interviewing Questionnaire will be prepared by the investigator which includes questions regarding demographic variables: Age, Gender, Occupation, Residence, Income, Health habits, Duration of COPD, Medications for COPD and Exposure to environmental pollutants.

Section B – This is in 2 parts

Part 1 – Assessment of selected respiratory parameters before and after intervention (respiratory rate and SpO₂).

Part 2 – This consist of finalized tool that is Modified Borg Dyspnea Scale is a tool used to assess the level of dyspnea or shortness of breath, experienced by a patient before and after the intervention. It is a subjective measure, where the patient rates their perceived level of breathlessness on a scale from 0 to 10, with 0 being no breathlessness and 10 being maximal breathlessness. Further, ask the patient to describe the difficulty of breathing and rate the described level of dyspnea under the grading categorized with score key and score grading between 1 to 4 i.e., no evidence of dyspnea, mild dyspnea, moderate dyspnea and severe dyspnea respectively.

Method of data collection:

1. Approval from the institutional ethics committee members and written permission from the head of the institution to conduct study was obtained.
2. Purpose of the research was explained to the participants.
3. Informed consent (written) was explained to the participants.
4. Formal permission was obtained from the concerned authority.
5. Subjects were taken from the selected hospitals using non-probability convenient sampling technique. The investigator introduced themselves and informed the samples about the nature of the study to ensure better co-operation during the data collection.
6. Objectives of the study and confidentiality of the data was discussed.
7. The data gathering process began from 05/12/2025 to 02/01/2026
8. Each subject was given a prepared tool containing
Section A – Consent form.
Section B - Tool for demographic variables.
Section C – Modified Borg Dyspnea Scale.
9. Assessed selected respiratory parameters with the use of pretest
10. Papworth Method was provided to the COPD patients
11. Post-test were collected on the day of five after intervention.

Statistical Methods

Descriptive statistics: Frequency and percentage distribution were used to describe demographic variables. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the pre-test and post-test.

Inferential statistics: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of Papworth Method on selected respiratory parameters among patients with COPD. Fisher's exact test for association between selected respiratory parameters and selected demographic variables.

Data analysis:

Sample size: For this study sample size, n comes to be 32.65. So approximately 35 samples were taken.

Eligibility criteria:

Inclusion criteria: Patients who are: -

diagnosed with COPD.

in the age group of 30-70 years.

stable without acute exacerbation in past 3 weeks.

willing to participate in the study.

able to understand English, Hindi and Marathi languages.

Exclusion criteria: Patients who are: -

on oxygen support.

having severe cognitive impairment.

having severe physical comorbidity.

having history of Lung surgery.

pregnant and lactating.

Withdrawal criteria:

Samples can withdraw from research at any point of time during the data collection.

RESULTS:**Findings related to demographic characteristics of the patients with COPD****Age group**

8.6% of the patients with COPD belongs to age group 30-40 years, 14.3% of the patients with COPD belongs to age group 40.1 to 50 years, 54.3% of the patients with COPD belongs to age group 50.1 to 60 years and 22.9% of the patients with COPD belongs to age group 60.1 to 70 years.

Gender

60% of patients were males and 40% of patients were females.

Occupation

34.3% of patients were farmers, 31.4% of patients had business, 17.1% of patients were labourers and 17.1% of patients were housewives.

Residence

28.6% of patients were from rural area and 71.4% of patients were from urban area.

Income

14.3% of patients had income less than Rs.5000, 22.9% of patients had income Rs.5001- Rs. 10000, 17.1% of patients had income Rs. 10001- Rs. 15000 and 45.7% of patients had income more than Rs. 15000.

Health habits

25.7% of patients had habit of tobacco, 37.1% of patients had habit of smoking, 20% of patients had habit of alcohol and 17.1% of patients did not have any habit.

Duration of COPD

34.3% of patients had duration of COPD less than 6 months, 25.7% of patients had duration of COPD 6.1 months to 1 year, 20% of patients had duration of COPD 1.1 to 2 years and 20% of patients had duration of COPD more than 2 years.

Medications for COPD

17.1% of patients were taking NSAIDs medications for COPD, 31.4% of patients were taking corticosteroids medications for COPD, 28.6% of patients were taking bronchodilators medications for COPD and 22.9% of patients had inhalers for COPD.

Exposure to environmental pollutants

100% of patients had exposure to environmental pollutants.

Analysis of data related to selected respiratory parameters among patients with COPD before implementation of Papworth Method.

Table 1: Dyspnea among patients with COPD before implementation of Papworth Method.

n=35

Dyspnea	Pretest	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No evidence of dyspnea	0	0.0%
Mild dyspnea	3	8.6%
Moderate dyspnea	20	57.1%
Severe dyspnea	12	34.3%

n=35

Fig 1: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution of pretest level of dyspnea of COPD patients.

8.6% of the patients with COPD had mild dyspnea, 57.1% of patients with COPD had moderate dyspnea and 34.3% of patients with COPD had severe dyspnea.

Table 2: Respiratory rate and SpO₂ among patients with COPD before implementation of Papworth Method.

n=35

Parameter		Pretest	
		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Respiratory rate	Abnormal	34	97.1%
	Normal	1	2.9%
SpO ₂	Abnormal	35	100.0%
	Normal	0	0.0%

n=35

Fig 2: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution of pretest score of respiratory rate and oxygen saturation of COPD patients.

97.1% of the patients with COPD had abnormal respiratory rate and 2.9% of patients had normal respiratory rate.

All the patients with COPD had abnormal SpO₂.

Analysis of data related to selected respiratory parameters among patients with COPD after implementation of Papworth Method

Table 3: Dyspnea among patients with COPD after implementation of Papworth Method

n=35

Dyspnea	Pretest		Post-test	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No evidence of dyspnea	0	0.0%	3	8.6%
Mild dyspnea	3	8.6%	22	62.9%
Moderate dyspnea	20	57.1%	10	28.6%
Severe dyspnea	12	34.3%	0	0.0%

n=35

Fig 3: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution of pretest and post-test level of dyspnea of among patients with COPD.

In pretest, 8.6% of the patients with COPD had mild dyspnea, 57.1% of patients had moderate dyspnea and 34.3% of patients had severe dyspnea. In post-test, 8.6% of the patients with COPD had no evidence of dyspnea, 62.9% of patients had mild dyspnea and 28.6% of patients had moderate dyspnea. It is evident that there is remarkable improvement in the level of dyspnea among patients with COPD after implementation of Papworth method.

Table 4: Respiratory rate and SpO2 among patients with COPD after implementation of Papworth Method

n=35

Parameter		Pretest		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Respiratory rate	Abnormal	34	97.1%	6	17.1%
	Normal	1	2.9%	29	82.9%
SpO2	Abnormal	35	100.0%	20	57.1%
	Normal	0	0.0%	15	42.9%

n=35

Fig 4: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution of pretest and post-test score of respiratory rates among patients with COPD.

In pretest, 97.1% of the patients with COPD had abnormal respiratory rate and 2.9% of patients had normal respiratory rate. In post-test, 17.1% of the patients with COPD had abnormal respiratory rate and 82.9% of patients had normal respiratory rate.

This indicates that there is remarkable improvement in respiratory rate after implementation of Papworth Method.

n=35

Fig 5: A bar diagram showing percentage distribution of pretest and post-test score of SpO2 among patients with COPD.

In pretest, all the patients with COPD had abnormal SpO2. In post-test, 57.1% of patients had abnormal SpO2 and 42.9% of them had normal SpO2.

This indicates that there is remarkable improvement in SpO2 after Papworth Method.

Table 5: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of Papworth Method on the level of dyspnea among patients with COPD

n=35

	Mean	SD	t-test	df	p-value
Pretest	5.7	1.7	30.9	34	<0.001
Post-test	2.5	1.7			

n=35

Fig 6: A bar diagram showing average score of pretest and post-test level of dyspnea among patients with COPD.

Researcher applied paired t-test for the effect of Papworth Method on the level of dyspnea among patients with COPD. Average dyspnea score among patients with COPD patients in pretest was 5.7 which reduced to 2.5 in post-test. T-value for this test was 30.9. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average dyspnea score in post-test was significantly lower than that in pretest. It is evident that the Papworth method is significantly effective in reducing the dyspnea among patients with COPD.

Table 6: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of Papworth Method on respiratory rate and SpO2 among patients with COPD.

n=35

Parameter		Mean	SD	t-test	df	p-value
Respiratory rate	Pretest	25.0	2.7	27.1	34	<0.001
	Post-test	18.6	1.8			
SpO2	Pretest	90.1	1.9	20.2	34	<0.001
	Post-test	93.9	1.7			

n=35

Fig 7: A bar diagram showing average score of pretest and post-test of respiratory rate among patients with COPD.

Researcher applied paired t-test for the effect of Papworth Method on respiratory rate among patients with COPD.

Average Respiratory rate among patients with COPD patients in pretest was 25 which reduced to 18.6 in post-test. T-value for this test was 27.1. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average Respiratory rate in post-test was significantly lower than that in pretest. It is evident that the Papworth method is significantly effective in reducing the respiratory rate among patients with COPD.

n=35

Fig 8: A bar diagram showing average score of pretest and post-test of SpO2 among patients with COPD.

Researcher applied paired t-test for the effect of Papworth Method on oxygen saturation among patients with COPD.

Average SpO₂ among patients with COPD patients in pretest was 90.1 which increased to 93.9 in post-test. T-value for this test was 20.2. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average SpO₂ in post-test was significantly higher than that in pretest. It is evident that the Papworth method is significantly effective in increasing the SpO₂ among patients with COPD.

Fisher's exact test for association between the level of dyspnea with selected demographic variables.

Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variable was found to have significant association with the level of dyspnea among patients with COPD.

Fisher's exact test for association between respiratory rate with selected demographic variables.

Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variable was found to have significant association with the respiratory rate among patients with COPD.

Irrespective of demographic data all patients had abnormal SpO₂.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Based on the present study, the investigator suggested the following recommendations.

A similar study may be replicated on large samples thereby findings can be generalized.

The study can be replicated in different settings.

The similar study can be conducted with different research designs and large samples.

The Papworth Method can be incorporated as a routine non-pharmacological nursing intervention in the management of patients with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease.

Comparative study can be undertaken to evaluate the effectiveness of the Papworth Method with other breathing techniques.

Future research can focus on assessing the long-term effectiveness of the Papworth Method on respiratory parameters and quality of life among COPD patients.

ABBREVIATIONS:

COPD: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

RR: Respiratory Rate

SpO₂: Oxygen saturation

WHO: World Health Organization

FEV₁: Expiratory Forced Volume in 1 second

FVC: Forced Vital Capacity

DISCUSSION:

The present study evaluated the effectiveness of the Papworth Method on selected respiratory parameters among patients with COPD. Baseline findings indicated that most patients experienced moderate to severe dyspnea, abnormal respiratory rate and reduced SpO₂ levels, reflecting compromised respiratory function prior to intervention.

Post-intervention analysis demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in all selected parameters. The mean dyspnea score decreased from 5.7 to 2.5 ($t = 30.9, p < 0.05$), respiratory rate reduced from 25 to 18.6 breaths/min ($t = 27.1, p < 0.05$) and mean SpO₂ increased from 90.1% to 93.9% ($t = 20.2, p < 0.05$). These findings indicate that the Papworth Method effectively improves breathing efficiency and oxygenation in COPD patients.

Overall, the findings suggest that the Papworth Method is an effective non-pharmacological intervention for improving respiratory outcomes among patients with COPD and its integration into routine clinical practice may enhance patient management and quality of life.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of the study revealed that the post-test respiratory parameters score were significantly improved when compared to pretest scores, indicating the effectiveness of Papworth Method. The intervention helped in improving breathing efficiency and reducing respiratory discomfort among patients with COPD. The Papworth Method is simple, safe, cost-effective and non-pharmacological nursing intervention that can be used as an adjunct to medical management in patients with COPD.

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